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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the Seshadripuram Journal of Social Sciences (SJSS), the flagship journal of the Seshadripuram Research Foundation (SRF), the research arm of the Seshadripuram Educational Trust (SET).

SJSS and SRF have their home and habitation at Seshadripuram First Grade College (SFGC), SET's A+ accredited higher education institution.

It is the avowed mission of SJSS to develop, promote, coordinate, and disseminate avant-garde developments and practises in the social sciences and bridge the gap between research and practise. SJSS has captured the attention of researchers across India and abroad as a forum for theoretical and conceptual research.

Living in a rapidly evolving world, SJSS is responsive to present challenges and anticipates and encounters future directions. Committed to quality but fair, flexible, and responsible in its editorial policy, SJSS is balanced, informative, insightful, and objective in its perspective on content.

I am immensely grateful to the editorial board of the journal, reviewers, and contributing authors. While I hope that this issue will be an enriching learning experience, your comments, feedback, suggestions, and scholarly contributions will be highly appreciated.

Happy Reading....

Dr. Wooday P Krishna

From the Desk of Principal

Dear Readers,

The Seshadripuram Journal of Social Sciences (SJSS), the research journal of the Seshadripuram Research Foundation (SRF), publishes high-quality research papers about current challenges and future directions in the field of social sciences.

Over the years, SJSS has become responsive not only to readers but to the relevant disciplines as well: informative, useful, creative, and responsive to present and changing trends. The journal has been carrying papers in subject areas that have a significant impact on thought and practise and future challenges and acting as a sounding board for dialogue.

Opening up new vistas of research, SJSS presents knowledge generated by academic thinking and reflection to a wide range of academics, practitioners, and policymakers. While mapping old territories, SJSS catches up with the accelerated pace of change in the social sciences through impactful research.

Thanks are due to the editorial team, reviewers, and contributing authors. We relish the overwhelming response of readers to past issues of SJSS and look forward to your valuable suggestions for future issues of the journal.

Happy Reading....

Dr S N Venkatesh

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**THE PRINCIPLE OF LAW AND GOVERNANCE REFLECTED IN
KAUṬILYA'S ARTHAŚĀSTRA**

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Abstract-

The *Kauṭilya's Arthaśāstra*, an ancient Indian text on political science and governance. This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the *Arthaśāstra*, its historical context, and the principles of governance and law that it espouses. The study examines the key features of Kauṭilya's philosophy of governance, including the role of the state, the nature of sovereignty, and the principles of justice and punishment. Additionally, the paper highlights the relevance of *Kauṭilya's Arthaśāstra* for contemporary debates on governance and law, demonstrating the enduring influence of this ancient text on political thought and practice. Overall, this research paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the principles of law and governance reflected in *Kauṭilya's Arthaśāstra*, shedding light on the enduring relevance of this seminal work for modern-day political discourse. The paper analyzes Kauṭilya's views on various aspects of governance, including the role of the ruler, the administration of justice, and the maintenance of law and order. It also explores the ways in which Kauṭilya's ideas have influenced Indian governance throughout history. Through an in-depth study of *Kauṭilya's Arthaśāstra*, the paper sheds light on the enduring principles of good governance and their relevance in contemporary times. This research paper examines the principle of law and governance as reflected in *Kauṭilya's Arthaśāstra*,

Key words-

Principle of law, Governance, Ancient India, Legal system, Political philosophy, Statecraft, Public administration, Policy-making, Judiciary Sovereignty, Power dynamics, Economic principles, Social welfare, Diplomacy, Military strategy.

Introduction:

The history of the tradition of Indian Politics is as old as the Vedas, and politics was known in the early *smṛtis* and *purāṇas*, as *Dandanīti*, whose content was crystallization of *Arthaśāstra* and *Dharmaśāstra* tradition. Through there are reference to the existence of political texts earlier than the fourth century BC. Perhaps the most popular and thoroughly scientific and authoritative interpretation of the tradition is the *Arthaśāstra* of Kauṭilya. This work is the quintessence of Aryan political wisdom as was interpreted and expounded by Bṛhaspati, Bharadvāja, Vātavyādhi, and others and illumined by Kauṭilya's genius. The discovery of Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra* has contributed much to the enrichment of the knowledge about ancient India Independence, we should be inclined to ante-date our existence, for occasional inspiration and guidance, to that period of classical antiquity when Kauṭilya, Chandragupta, Bindusara and Ashoka, by a supreme effort of the soul, realized for mankind, a distinctive and a unique political experience, not yet repeated even imperfectly, in any part of world since then.

The Conception of Law and Administration-

The object of Aristotle was to re-adapt Law to the promotion of virtue and noble living.¹ Reason was the principle which inspired the social organism and this was embodied in Law. Reason made articulate was Law. It was free from prejudice and was the public conscience of the community. Aristotle says in his Ethics.² Law is reason without desire. Law has on the one hand, a compelling power; and constraint is a voluntary one. Law is moral compulsion which freemen can impose upon themselves. It has two voices, a voice of stern compulsion: it is the higher self of the citizen. Therefore, the law-giver is a moral teacher of righteousness. His duty is to preserve the acts that ought to be done and also to reveal and inspire in man the true motives of action.

Law was not a code of prohibitions, nor was it limited to the corrective justice of the law Courts. Its range was wider than morality itself, and institutions were the creations of law; traditions and customs rested on its sanction. All ideas of society were molded by it and Law was blended with religion, with morality and public opinion and by its subtle operation subjected the society to its will.

Law was invested with spiritual efficacy and power. Law was a divine element immanent

in human nature. Aristotle notes that the worst fault of untendered democracy was its lawlessness, and the reign of arbitrary will and thus entailing a condition of negation of freedom, the dethronement of reason and the predominance of clashing impulses.³ Plato says in his *Laws*, VI, 702 “The service of the Laws is also the service of the Gods, a service in which to obey is nobler than to rule”; and this implied the voluntary subordination of the individual will to the will of the community.

Kauṭilya too, like Aristotle holds frank companionship with thoughts that had paralyzed early *sāstrakāra*'s into inactivity. We feel in *Arthaśāstra* that we are in an upper and serener air in which man's spiritual and intellectual freedom through a *Dharmic* state is assured. Like the Greeks, the Hindus too had to fight for the Law as for their King, for Law was their supreme master, and they neither praised the life of anarchy nor the life of despotism. Humblest freedom was neither the Greek conception of freedom nor that of Kauṭilya. Kauṭilya is the interpreter of Neo Aryanism against the nihilistic anarchy of Buddhism, as Aristotle was the interpreter of Hellenism as against prevalent barbarism. Kauṭilya, like Aristotle, in the name of Dharma appeals to the sense of honour and of duty and to human dignity, to moral responsibility and to enlightened patriotism. Neither tyranny nor *Arājaka*, but ordered liberty satisfied Kauṭilya and this implied a delicate adjustment, and of combination of principles apparently opposite, and of harmonizing conflicting claims; for the Hindus like the Greeks, possessed a sense of flexibility and a faculty of compromise.

Kauṭilya knew that the State which revolves within its breast, only social and religious problems was bound to be weak politically. The Aryans in order to make the religious conquest of the world had not emphasized the importance of social cohesion and co-ordination through political integration. Kauṭilya realized, like Aristotle, that the State integrated under a strong government could be a great civilizer and the disturber and regenerator of slumbering societies, and at the same time, the source of most of the quickening ideas which remake societies and renovate literature and art. The two tendencies summed up in Brahmanical Hinduism and Buddhism often regarded as opposing and irreconcilable forces are perfectly harmonized in Kauṭilya, for Buddhism stood for freedom for society, freedom for the individual and freedom for thought, while Brahmanical Hinduism stood for supremacy of mind over sense, of spirit over matter.

Kauṭilya's conception of Law was in keeping with his conception of Politics freed from the trammels of irrationalism. Law was not an expression of the common will of the people, and all Hindu law-givers agreed in preferring the origin of law as *śṛti*. Whatever knowledge that was not syllogistically worked out but was derived by flashes of intuition, was regarded as inspired knowledge; and customs like-wise which had been handed down from the past were also sacred. Historically, tradition and usage were the primary sources of the foundation of Law. *smṛti* as a source of Law referred to *śīla*, practices and recollections of those who knew the *Vedas* as sources of law.

The authority of long established custom was never questioned by any society, Greek or Roman, and all regarded that Law was something which all men ought to obey, chiefly because every law was devised and given by God, and made intelligible by its being resolved by intelligent men. Law was invariably looked upon as founded on the twin roots of religion and on agreement of men learned in sacred lore. Thus, the community always revered the Assemblies of wise men and vested authority in them. The greatest importance was given to *śiṣṭācāra*, viz., practices, of men who knew the *Vedas* and who acted in society, not from any obvious earthly motives but with a spirit of altruism and of conformity to *Dharma*. *śiṣṭas* are described by *Baudhāyana* as those who are free from desire '*RāgaDveṣādiParityāga*' who are free from envy, from pride, contented with a store of grain sufficient for ten days, free from covetousness, free from hypocrisy, greed, perplexity and anger; who in accordance with the sacred law have studied the *Veda* together with its appendages, who know how to draw inferences from them and are able to adduce proofs perceptible by the senses and free from the revealed texts.⁴

This description of *śiṣṭa* envisages true Brahmanical character which was devotion to God and parents, good temper, freedom from jealousy and bitterness, fair speaking, gratitude, piety, and tranquility. *Ācāra* indicated practices which sought to follow practices of previous good men. Though custom and practices looked authoritarian, the abrogative function of custom was bound to develop in the absence of any effective repealing agency which was to adapt *Dharma* to progressive popular opinion. *Nārada* and *Yājñavalkya* specifically mention that *Dharma* which was condemned by people should not be followed.⁵ According to Kauṭilya, the sayings of learned men along with *Vedas*, *Purāṇas*, *Itihāsas*, *Nyāya* and *Aṅga* were all sources of *Dharma*. All these studies were regarded as the completion of the *Vedic* knowledge and so far as any of them gave any guidance, it was entitled to be looked upon as a foundation for *dharma*. Kauṭilya mentions of

Ānvīkṣikī, *Sāṃkhya*, *Yoga* and *Lokāyata* sciences applied to matters of religion and law.⁶ The Secular body of law founded partly on custom and partly on the authority of the various texts was also recognized as a source of *Dharma* which was understood as a property of the soul. *ĀtmaḡuṇāhDharma*. Secular law existed side by side with sacred law. Outside the pale of sacred law, persons were governed by their own customs and by the ordinances of their own communal organization; and the king was required to maintain the *Samayas* as well as whatever were their religious customs and institutions.

Law was related to the environment, the social and legal institutions of the times, the social ends and ideas and the entire culture of the Age. Social ends determined the content of law, and the relativity of law to ends extended from content even to form and source. The sources of law were pre-eminently determined by the ends contemplated by the society to which the law applied and varied with a change in social ends and ideas.

Kautilyarecognized the importance of rational law or king's law laws and its priority to *Dharma*, *Vyavahāra*, and *Caritra*. The king's law was to be in accordance with the injunctions of the triple Vedas wherein the four *Varṇas* and *Āśramas* are defined; the king could not overlook caste duties which were eternal. But he could makeand these were only regulatory laws and not laws substantive which would make him arbitrary. The king could promulgate fresh out these could be done by superseding the *śāstras*, when the laws had their basic principles rooted in *Dharma*. The judges versed in the *Dharmaśāstras* could demand conformity to *Dharma*, but as the judges were at the mercy of the king, the interpretations of the law could be liberal and the king as in the case of Emperor Asoka could turn out to be a legislator rigorously enforcing protection of animal life and seriously circumscribing the liberty of the orthodox.

Law was rationalistic, in the sense, a rule or behavior to which men were to conform, was itself a part of the natural order of things. The Greeks too believed in *Thamis*, laws as ordained by Heaven, or nature, *Dilke* that which was abstractly right, and *Nomos*, secular laws originating either in established usage or Governmental enactment. The greater part of Greek law as Indian law was unwritten, being reduced to concrete activation by ad hoc pronouncements of magistrates specially revered for learning and wisdom. Law was common sense and right reason in the form of specific rules of human action.

Kaṇṭakaśodhana:

Kautilya makes a clear distinction between civil law *Dharmasthiya* and penal law, *Kaṇṭakaśodhana*. Three ministers of the king *amātyas* and three learned men acquainted with sacred law.

Dharmastas were required to carry on the administration of justice. They determined cases relating to duels robbery and disputes among trade guilds. They distinguished between valid and invalid transactions, declared the offences of *Parokta* and *Dr̥ṣṭaDoṣa* and *Svayamvada* as faulty and *Anuyoga*, honesty *ārjava*, evidence *hetu* and assertion by oath *śapatha* as important steps for success, *Arthasādhaka*.

Penal law was a part of public law, and all such rules of law that concerned the functions of administration in relation to administrative authorities among themselves and in the relation of the administration with artisans. Labour unions *Samghas*, trader merchant associations and foreigners, were regarded *Kaṇṭakaśodhana* Law.⁷ It was intended to carry out the king's law in its minutest details, regulate the administrative organizations of the *Rāṣṭra* and determine the rules of law relative to the activity of the administrative authorities. It was to indicate the right of *Kārukaśilpagaṇah* which the ministers were to respect and thus delimit the sphere of action of the administration so far as the unions and corporations of artisans were concerned; it was also a method of offering individual remedies for the violation of the rights of corporations. *Kaṇṭakaśodhana* was manifestly something more comprehensive than a body of penal sanctions which were applied to all the castes and corporations. There commissioners *Pradeshtarāh* were required to deal with measures to suppress disturbance to peace. Persons learned in customary and sacred law had no place in adjudication of penal cases, as *Kaṇṭakaśodhana* was secular and vitally connected with day to day measures of administration and *Rājaśāsana*. Weavers, washer men, scavengers, medical practitioners, musicians, beggars and buffoons who were all thieves in effect though not in name by cultivating fraudulent practices, were restrained from oppression on the country. The individual was protected against the malpractices of merchants. The Superintendent of Commerce supervised weights and measures to prevent deception, secured an equitable distribution of commodities, centralized sales in cases of urgency and fixed the percentage of profit to the merchants and regulated prices of commodities on consideration of their outlay, quantity, amount of toll, hire and other kinds of accessory expenses. The king was to provide remedies against such calamities as fire, floods, pestilences, famines, wild beasts and spirits and demons. Against calamities *upanipatepratīkārāh* Kauṭilya suggests not only physical but also supernatural remedies. *Atharvavedavidomāyayogavidovakarmanīkuryuḥ*.

In exercising remedies, the king had to protect the afflicted among his people as a father his sons *SarvatraChopahatanpītevanugr̥hniyat*. The commissioner *Samāharttā* was to protect the people against the wickedness of *gudhajivi* whose avocations were foul and were carried out in a insidious and mysterious manner. Kauṭilya mentions of thirteen kinds of criminals who secretly while attempting⁸ to live by foul means destroy the peace of the *Rāṣṭra*. Kauṭilya commends the employment of even ascetic spies to detect youths of criminal propensities.⁹ Persons whose family subsists on slender means of inheritance, who frequently change their residence, caste and names, who conceal their own avocations and take to luxurious modes of life, who are excessively attached to women, squander away their money, and

whose destination and transactions are difficult to understand, had to be apprehended on suspicion.¹⁰ Criminals had to be seized on suspicion or in the very act or on the basis of circumstantial evidence by officers like *pradeshta*, *sthānika*, and *nāgarika* in charge of a fortified town. But the production of conclusive evidence was necessary before the accused was charged by the offence and punishment meted out to him *samaptakaranamniyamayet*.¹¹

Kauṭilya denounces acts of murder or inducement to murder under infatuation of love, anger or other sinful passions. Suicide under the influence of passions is likewise deprecated, as life is sacred, and what is intended for dedication to service being violently removed due to personal infatuation. Accordingly, bodies of such persons or of those who induced suicide should be dragged along the public road by the hands of *Chāṇḍalas* and obsequies denied to them in order to demonstrate to the people the ugliness and immorality of suicide. *Ghatayetsvayamatmanamstrivapapenamohita*.¹² Though different kinds of tortures were employed to extract confession, women, the weak and the infirm and those who made confessions of their own accord were exempted from torture; but no difference was observed between the castes as regards punishment for crimes, and even Brahman offenders were branded to a wound and the nature of their crime was proclaimed in public and they were banished.

Kauṭilya advocates the infliction of very severe penalties on government officers and others who were guilty of misappropriation or of damage to state property, like granaries, treasure, mines and manufactories. Issue or use of unauthorized orders by officers was punished in proportion to the gravity of the crime; even the judges were punished for intimidation, unnecessary inquiries and delay in the discharge of duty, evasion and imposition of unjust corporal punishment. The king was required to test the conduct of government servants and then, through those officers of approved character had to examine the conduct of his people both in towns and villages. It was the duty of the commissioners to determine the propriety of imposing fines in lieu of mutilation of limbs, taking into consideration, the social position of persons, the nature of the offence and of the cause that led to the perpetration of the offence, the antecedent and present circumstances, time and place and equitable distinctions among offenders. Kauṭilya devotes two interesting chapters for the discussion of the status and freedom of women in society and the meting out of punishment for violating justice. Traders and merchants were protected against individuals and

government servants; likewise, mature and immature women were protected from the sinister designs of the wicked. The Superintendents of land *Chorarajjukas* and even the people of the locality were required to make good, losses of merchandise sustained by traders and merchants; thus the latter were assured absolute security of person and property.¹³ Kaṭilya recommends likewise, elaborate measures to detect crimes from seditious persons or those guilty of treason against the king.

By means of *Dharmasthīya* and *Kaṅṭakaśodhana* law and administration, the *Svāmī* had to consolidate his kingdom and exercise benevolent but absolute sovereignty over the *Rāṣṭra*. Animated by enlarged ideas of ethnic and territorial unity, the *Svāmī* entered upon the realization of a positive policy and endeavored to bring under one sovereignty and under one administration, all fragments of territory and people that formed a natural whole for purposes of commerce, social intercourse and defense. To accomplish this purpose, the *Svāmī* entered upon a career of aggression which necessitated a perfect internal cohesion; and accordingly, all interests, family and religion were subordinated to *Svāmī* and centralized administration; and divine qualities were imputed to the king by the wise men *prajñā* and he was encouraged to assert absolute powers in all matters of government and society as crises and emergencies demanded strength, vigor, energy of action, promptness of decision, unity of counsel, continuity and consistency of policy. The real work of the administration had to be done by ministers of the bureaucracy, with a permanent status and tenure and selected for their administrative capacity, tact and resourcefulness. Coordination, regulation and control, initiative and encouragement were the functions of ministers and heads of departments, and the entire hierarchy of officers was to achieve good and efficient administration by undivided counsel, promptness of decisions and a consistent policy.

Accordingly, the responsibilities of *amātyas*, *anujīvi*, *bhṛtyas* and others who were all dedicated to the service of the *Svāmī* were great and heavy. The king's moods were to be closely followed by the courtiers and difficult situations had to be overcome by great vigilance, tact and care. The courtier had always to guard the king's interest and his own interests and others in conformity to the principles of righteousness and economy.¹⁴ The courtier was to avoid evil aspersions against others and he should not ascribe evil to others, he should forgive evil done to himself and to develop as much forbearance as the earth. *Kṣhmāvānprthivisamaḥ*, for, the life of a courtier under the service of a king was like life in fire *Āṅgavivahisamproktavṛttirajopijīvinam*. He was to endeavour to arrest the fall of the king into evil habits and save him from the intrigues,

plots and deceptions of enemies *Mantrasamvaranarthmacharantiprājñah*. When *artha* and honour were discontinued by the king, the minister was to abandon such a king; but if the king was a *śīlamātmanamśca*, the minister was to rectify his own defects and loyally serve the king.

The responsibilities of the ministers at the time of the apprehended death of the king were grave, as apathy and neglect on their part would involve the state in peril. Accordingly, to Kauṭilya, the ministers like the philosopher kings of Plato were the inspiration and the fundamental urge of state activity; they were the props of the king's authority, and they guided his destiny which was bound up with the state's destiny with a firm hand, conducting the administration themselves. In times of grave crisis and national calamity, when the report of the death of the Swami would imperil the kingdom, the ministers played the role of national conscience and of Providence and averted *rājyavyasanās* in the form of enemy invasions, by great courage and statesmanship. The army and the treasury had to be safeguarded; cognates, princes and other chiefs of the royal family had to be withdrawn from the capital and sent on difficult expeditions, wild tribes, disaffected elements and neighboring kings who threatened invasions had to be conciliated; the heir-apparent then, had to be brought out of the palace and displayed before the public and then, the burdens of administration transferred to his shoulders. *Bharadvāja* advocates usurpation of authority by the minister, in times of disputed succession, *svayamrājyamgrnhiyat*, and the minister was not to discard what had of its own accord fallen to his hands; for, then, the people would say that a woman making love of her own accord will, when discarded, curse the man. *Svayamārūdhahi strītyajyamānābhishapatītiLoka pravādah*.¹⁵ Kauṭilya recommends that the minister should invest himself with the powers of sovereignty, during the interregnum in order to consolidate the kingdom *evamek. aiśvaryamatyaḥkārayet*, but it is unrighteous to do an act which excites popular fury. The minister was to install in the kingdom such a prince who possessed kingly qualities *rajaputramatyasampanamraiasthapayet*; with the help of *mahamatras* and members of the royal family.¹⁶ He was to address them thus: Look at the father of this boy as well as to your own valour and descent; this Kumara is only a flag and you are the lords.¹⁷ The minister was thus to persuade the *yogapuruṣas* to an acceptance of his choice should commend the minister's lead in the matter with the sacred object of protecting the kingdom. *Koanyabhavatpurogatasmatragnaschaturvarnyamarhatipalayatumiti*. It was open to the ministers after having consolidated the kingdom and taught the new *Svāmī* in the principles

of polity illustrated from *Itihāsa* and *Purāṇa*, to seek retirement from active life and migrate to the woods in the garb of an accomplished ascetic for contemplation, *AranyamDhirgasatramva seveta*.¹⁸

Kauṭilya is a great exponent of the doctrine of the rule of the aristocracy in the Aristotelian sense of the rule of the noblest and the best. The aristocracy of ministers was to serve *Svāmī* loyally, and to immolate themselves at his altar if need be; but normally, the ministers were Swami's guides and the custodians of his conscience.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra* is a remarkable ancient Indian text that provides valuable insights into the principles of law and governance. This text is not only a comprehensive treatise on statecraft but also a repository of knowledge on various aspects of public administration, ethics, morality, economic principles, social welfare, diplomacy, and military strategy. The *Arthaśāstra* reflects Kauṭilya's deep understanding of the complex interplay between power dynamics and governance, and his vision for a just and prosperous society.

Through its detailed discussion of various institutions and practices related to law and governance, the *Arthaśāstra* remains relevant even in the modern era. This text has influenced the development of legal systems and political philosophy not only in India but also in other parts of the world. By studying the *Arthaśāstra*, scholars can gain a better understanding of the principles that underpin effective governance and the challenges that are inherent in creating and maintaining a just and prosperous society. Overall, the *Arthaśāstra* is an invaluable resource for anyone interested in the study of law, governance, and political philosophy. Its enduring relevance and importance are a testament to the enduring legacy of Kauṭilya, who remains one of the most important thinkers in the history of Indian civilization.

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